

Experimental and numerical study of the large-scale testing of composite bearings

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SUMMARY

This study includes an experimental and numerical study of the large-scale testing of fiber reinforced polymeric composite bearings. The kinematics of the test setup is simulated with two-dimensional plane-strain model with finite element method. Simulation results correspond closely to the experimental data, and provide careful investigation of stresses distribution in the bearing.

Keywords: composite bearing, finite element analysis, large-scale testing, tribology

INTRODUCTION

The self-lubricating properties of some polymeric materials make them very valuable in bearing applications. When these materials are reinforced with high resistance fibers such as carbon fibers, glass fibers or polyester fibers, they are able to operate under conditions which conventional bearings can not [1]. At present there are few numerical studies about composite journal bearings for heavy loadings, and the degradation mechanisms of these bearings are hardly understood. In this article the mechanical behavior of a fiber reinforced polymeric composite bearing is studied. To this purpose a new test apparatus is designed and manufactured.

In conventional tribotesting, small-scale tests are mainly used because of their cost effectiveness, time efficiency, and the easiness of handling of small samples. However, because clearances and pressure distribution can not always be scaled properly, conditions can strongly differ from the real application scale, and extrapolating towards the real working conditions occasionally results in significant errors. From this point of view, experimental setups in which full-scale bearings can be tested statically and dynamically are very important. A test rig should be able to measure the friction torque accurately between journal and bearing. Usually, indirect methods are used in test rigs for journal bearings, and only few can measure friction torques by direct methods [2]. In indirect methods the measured torque includes the friction of both the test bearing and the shaft-supporting bearings. These two elements cannot be separated in an easy way. The developed test setup uses a direct method where the friction torque of only the test bearing is measured without any interference of the shaft-supporting bearings.

Although the experimental method provides the required information to study the magnitude of the forces on the bearing, it does not give detailed information about the distribution of stresses in the contact area between the bearing and shaft. Therefore in order to study the distribution of the shear stresses, the normal stresses, and the effects of the allocated tolerances in the set-up, numerical simulations are employed. In this article the kinematics of the test rig is modeled as a simplified two-dimensional plane strain model by FEM method.

TEST RIG

The experimental studies are done with a new test rig which is designed to determine the tribological behavior of large-scale journal bearings subjected to a reciprocating angular movement. Figure 1 presents the test rig and its cross-sectional view. This apparatus has been considered to test composite bearings with inner diameter of 300 millimeters. The loading conditions, rotation speed, and rotation angle can be changed by user at any time during the test. The friction torque is determined by measuring the force acting on a lever arm connected to the bushing. The tests are driven by a closed-loop servo-hydraulic system. All measuring signals are registered continuously and digitally by means of a data acquisition card. This apparatus provides measurement of the normal and friction force between the bearing and shaft, bearing's temperature during the application, and wear rate of the bearing's surface.

1-Composite bearing	5-Drive piston	8-load-cell(friction torque)	11-Load transmission trolley
2-Bushing	6-Drive lever arm	9-Hydraulic actuator	12-Backing
3-Shaft	7-Bushing lever arm	10-Load-cell (vertical load)	13-Shaft bushing
4-Shaft support			

Figure 1 a: Large-scale test setup. b: Components of the test setup. c: Cross-sectional view

The test is started by applying the vertical force on the bushing component by hydraulic actuator, and then the drive piston starts to reciprocate and makes the rotational oscillation in the shaft.

KINEMATICS OF THE TEST SETUP

Friction force plays a very important role in tribological analyses. Therefore evaluation of the coefficient of friction (COF) of materials in tribosystems is a key factor. In this

study, the COF between the composite bearing and steel shaft is calculated by using the measured signals.

Figure 2 depicts a schematic view of the loading and kinematics of the test rig. The parameters of the figure are; F_P : loading actuator force, F_L : force on the load-cell, F_F : friction force between the composite bearing and shaft, F_N : normal force on composite bearing, R_S : shaft radius, R_b : bearing radius, R_L : distance between the action points of F_P and F_L , and α : rolling angle.

Figure 2 Schematics of the acting forces and kinematics of the setup. a: Acting forces, b: Kinematics

During the test F_P is assumed to be constant, and although due to a very small deviation of the hydraulic piston from its position, it is supposed to be vertical. Since the displacement of the bushing remains small, the force in the load cell F_L can also be considered vertical. According to the Coulomb law [3], coefficient of friction is the ratio of the tangential and normal reaction force components:

$$\mu = \frac{F_F}{F_N} \quad (1)$$

F_F and F_N are derived from the following equilibrium equations:

$$F_F = \frac{R_L}{R_b} \cdot F_L \quad (2)$$

$$F_N = \left[(F_P + F_L)^2 - \left(F_L \cdot \frac{R_L}{R_b} \right)^2 \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (3)$$

With substituting the obtained equations for F_F and F_N from Equations 2 and 3 in equation 1, the COF becomes:

$$\mu = \tan \alpha = \frac{1}{\left[\left(\frac{R_b}{R_L} \right)^2 \cdot \left(\frac{F_P + F_L}{F_L} \right)^2 \right]^{\frac{1}{2}}} \quad (4)$$

In the journal bearing application when the shaft starts to rotate, the bearing will initially roll up to a certain angle of inclination and will then start to slip [4, 5]. Therefore, if the shaft rotates continuously, after the first rolling step the process reaches to the steady state sliding conditions. The tangent of the inclination angle is the COF. If the elastic deformation of the load cell and the clearances of its connections at both sides are ignored, the kinematics of the shaft rolling in the bearing can be expressed as:

$$\left(\frac{d\beta}{dt} - \frac{d\theta}{dt} \right) / \left(\frac{d\varphi}{dt} - \frac{d\theta}{dt} \right) = \frac{R_s}{R_b} \quad (5)$$

In this equation $\frac{d\beta}{dt}$, $\frac{d\theta}{dt}$, and $\frac{d\varphi}{dt}$ describe respectively, rotating velocity of the bushing, rotating velocity of the shaft center, and rotating velocity of the shaft around its center. Since the lever arm prevents the rotation of the bushing, $\frac{d\beta}{dt} = 0$, the eq. (5) will be simplified into:

$$-\frac{d\theta}{dt} / \left(\frac{d\varphi}{dt} - \frac{d\theta}{dt} \right) = \frac{R_s}{R_b} \quad (6)$$

Solving the equation will result into:

$$\varphi = \theta \cdot \frac{R_s - R_b}{R_s} \quad (7)$$

Once the angle θ reaches to α , this relation is no longer valid because the shaft starts to slide instead of rolling. In practice the static COF differs from the dynamic COF. Therefore there are two rolling angles α_s and α_D , which correspond to the static and dynamic coefficient of friction. Once the shaft starts to rotate, it rolls up to $\theta = \alpha_s$, and then drops to $\theta = \alpha_D$ and sliding occurs in the contact [6].

FINITE ELEMENT MODELING

Although the experimental method provides a good estimate of the forces on the bearing, it does not give detailed information about the contact stress distribution. Therefore in order to study the stress distribution, numerical simulations are employed. In this article the kinematics of the test rig is modeled by FEM method.

The traditional method of analyzing these kinds of rolling and sliding contacts is Lagrangian formulation. In the Lagrangian approach, the nodal points are attached to material points, thus the motion of the material during the process is followed. Hence, it is easy to follow the history of material deformation. The Lagrangian analysis is computationally expensive since a transient analysis must be performed and very fine meshing is required on the shaft surface.

Another possibility to simulate this problem is the Eulerian method in which attention is focused on the motion of the material through a stationary control volume. The advantage in this method is that Eulerian elements do not deform with the material. Therefore, regardless of the magnitude of the deformation in process, Eulerian elements retain their original shape.

The limitation of the Eulerian method is simulation of the free boundaries. In this approach, it is harder to follow the material deformation history since the mesh is fixed in space and is not distorted. However, the boundary of the deformation region should be known a priori, because it can not be easily updated during the deformation. Indeed, if in an Eulerian simulation the boundaries of the model change, new control volumes have to be created, which is difficult to deal with [7].

An alternative approach which combines the advantages of both Lagrangian and Eulerian formulations is the Mixed Lagrangian-Eulerian method. In this approach, the mesh can have a motion independent of material deformation. Therefore, the motion of the mesh can be designed in accordance with the nature of deformation, and thus mesh distortion is avoided on one hand and the boundaries are updated on the other [8].

In this article two dimensional kinematics of the test setup is simulated as a quasi static model by the Mixed Lagrangian-Eulerian method.

Figure 1 demonstrates that the geometry of the bearing and bushing consists of uniformly extruded sections along the shaft's axis. In addition, the hydraulic piston applies a uniformly spread pressure on the bushing along the same axis. Therefore, considering the width of the bearing (120 mm), which is long enough to prevent the strain in the axial direction, a two-dimensional plane strain model can provide careful investigation of the stress distribution on the bearing as well as the kinematic modeling of the setup.

Figure 3 depicts the boundary conditions and meshing of the two-dimensional plane strain model for the test rig. The model contains 16939 high accuracy second order elements. This simplified assembly includes the bearing, bushing, shaft, loading actuator (piston), load transmission trolley, load-cell, support, hinge A (connection of load-cell and bushing), and hinge B (connection of load-cell and support).

Figure 3 2D finite element model.

FRICTION AND MATERIAL MODELLING

In the numerical simulation it is assumed that the friction coefficient decays exponentially from the static value to the dynamic value (see figure 4) according to the formula:

$$\mu = \mu_D + (\mu_S - \mu_D) e^{-d_c \dot{\gamma}_{eq}} \quad (8)$$

Where μ_D is the dynamic friction coefficient, μ_S is the static friction coefficient, d_c is a user-defined decay coefficient, and $\dot{\gamma}_{eq}$ is the slip rate [9]. Regarding the experimental data, parameters of the equation are defined and then the friction coefficient will be calculated correlated to the slip rate.

Figure 4 Relation between COF and slip rate.

The test bearing is a composite of a phenolic resin, polyester reinforcing fibers, and PTFE filling for internal lubrication (see figure 5). This bearing is an orthotropic material with the engineering constants shown in the table 1.

Figure 5 Composite bearing

Table 1 Engineering constants of the composite bearing, r: Radial coordinate, t: Tangential coordinate, z: Axial coordinate

E_{rr}	2.75 GPa	G_{rt}	1.00 GPa	ν_{rt}	0.165
E_{tt}	10.00 GPa	G_{tz}	4.00 GPa	ν_{tz}	0.250
E_{zz}	10.00 GPa	G_{rz}	1.00 GPa	ν_{rz}	0.068

RESULTS

The tests were performed on a composite bearing under the conditions shown in table 2:

Table 2 Test conditions.

<i>Bearing diameter:</i>	300 (mm)
<i>Bearing thickness</i>	25 (mm)
<i>Normal load by loading actuator</i>	100 (kN)
<i>Driving piston amplitude</i>	5 (mm)
<i>Driving piston frequency</i>	0.5 (Hz)
<i>Clearance between shaft and bearing</i>	1.1 (mm)
<i>Clearance between the load cell pins and correlated bushing</i>	0.1 (mm)

Figure 6 shows the experimental results for the coefficient of friction between the composite bearing and the shaft.

Figure 6 Measured values of the drive piston's displacement and calculated values of the coefficient of friction between the composite bearing and shaft.

Figure 7 compares the extracted friction force (F_F) from the experimental measurements and numerical simulations. Due to the static coefficient of friction at the start of each cycle the friction force graph shows a spike, and when sliding occurs, it decreases. It is obvious that when direction of the rotation changes, the direction of the friction force also changes. These figures show that there is a very good agreement between numerical and experimental results. At the start of each cycle when rolling contact occurs between the shaft and bearing, the friction force rises till 14.5 kN and then it decreases to 11.5 kN in the sliding condition.

Figure 7 Friction force between the composite bearing and shaft. F_F : friction force, DISP: displacement of driving piston.

The fluctuation in the friction force generates a relative variation in the normal force between bearing and shaft. Once the direction of the friction force changes, the normal force reduces. The normal force at the counterclockwise rotation increases up to 101.2 kN, while it decreases to 96.7 kN in the clockwise rotation of the shaft (see figure 8).

Figure 8 Normal force between the composite bearing and shaft. F_N : normal force, DISP: displacement of driving piston, F_p : applied load by loading piston.

Figure 9 shows that the simulation results of the horizontal displacement of the bushing precisely correspond with the test results. At the moment that the shaft motion tends to overcome the static friction force, the bearing sticks to the shaft. At this moment the bushing system moves forward or backward depending on the direction of rotation. Once the contact condition changes from rolling to sliding, the bearing slides back and the shaft slides against the bearing in a fixed position. The horizontal displacement of the bushing varies between +0.1 and -0.1 mm.

Figure 9 FEM results of the horizontal displacement of the bushing, H. DISP: Horizontal displacement of bushing, DISP: displacement of driving piston

Figure 10 shows the four steps of the radial stress distribution in the composite bearing. Step 1 shows the free bearing without any loading. After applying 100 kN force, radial stress in the bearing is built up. In the second step the stresses are symmetrically

distributed along the loading axis, and the maximum radial stress in the center of the contact line equals 8.5 MPa. After the loading is completed and reaches 100 kN, the shaft starts to rotate in the clockwise direction. By rotating the shaft, the stress contours starts to move to the left and at the sliding point remain fixed (see step 3), and when the shaft rotates in the counterclockwise direction, stress contours move to the right (see step 4).

Figure 10 Radial stress distribution on the composite bearing.

CONCLUSION

Although the experimental method provides a general view of the friction force of the composite bearing, it does not give enough data to investigate the stress distribution in the bearing contact area. Numerical simulations do not only include the correct kinematics of the large-scale loading set-up, but provide also the frictional shear stresses and normal stress distribution along the contact line of the bearing and shaft.

Considering the cost of the experimental methods in large scale testing, these simulation results are very helpful tools to analyze and predict the effect of the mechanical design parameters and material properties of the composite bearing in the journal bearings application.

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REFERENCES

1. Dai Gil, L. and K. Seong Su, Failure analysis of asbestos-phenolic composite journal bearing. *Composite Structures*, 2004. 65(1): p. 37-46.

2. A. Biyiklioglu, H.C., H. Adatepe, H. Bas, M.S. Duman, A New Test Apparatus and Method for Friction Force Measurement in Journal Bearings under Dynamic Loading. *Experimental Techniques*, 2005.
3. Persson, B.N.J., *Sliding Friction: Physical Principles and Applications*. 1998, Springer. p. 13.
4. Beek, A.v., *Machine Lifetime Performance and Reliability*. 2004: Delft University of Technology. 432.
5. J. Van Wittenberghe, W.Ost., A. Rezaei, P. De Baets, L. Zsidai, G. Kalácska Test Setup For Frictional Force Measurements of Large-Scale COMPOSITE BEARINGS. *Experimental Techniques* 2008.
6. Friedrich, K., Goda, Tibor, Varadi, Karoly, Wetzels, Bernd, Finite Element Simulation of the Fiber–Matrix Debonding in Polymer Composites Produced by a Sliding Indentor: Part I – Normally Oriented Fibers. *Journal of COMPOSITE MATERIALS*, 2004. 38(18/2004): p. 1583-1606.
7. Bathe, K.-J., *Finite Element Procedures*. 1996: Prentice Hall.
8. Ted Belytschko, W.K.L., Brian Moran, *Nonlinear Finite Element for Continua and Structures*. 2000, John Wiley & Sons. p. pp. 393-443.
9. Oden, J.T. and J.A.C. Martins, Models and Computational Methods for Dynamic Friction Phenomena. *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering*, 1985. 52(1-3): p. 528-634.